

Complexes of Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with some Diimine (N₂O₂) Schiff Base Ligands containing Non-coordinating Azomethine Nitrogen Atom

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The identified tautomeric forms of Schiff bases may be enolamine and ketoenamine besides recently characterised tautomer namely zwitterionic (charge separated) form^{1,2}. In zwitterionic form, coordination takes place through the negatively charged oxygen atom and anions that are added to Schiff base in the form of metal salt for complex formation.

So far no attempt is made in the literature³ for the synthesis and characterisation of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes with Schiff

bases containing aromatic bridges, viz. salicylaldehyde orthophenylenediimine (Salophen), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde *o*-phenylenediimine (Nalophen), salicylaldehyde metaphenylenediimine (Salmphen) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde metaphenylenediimine (Nalmphen). In continuation of our efforts to study coordination complexes with N₄, S₄, N₂S₂ and N₂O₂ ligands⁴, herein we present the synthesis and characterisation of Group IIB metal complexes with wider variation of ligands than have been available earlier.

Results and Discussion

The complexes of Zn, Cd and Hg with Salophen, Nalophen, Salmphen and Nalmphen (Table 1) are not soluble in methanol or ethanol but readily dissolve in chloroform, toluene, dimethyl-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analyses (%) : Found/(Calcd.)				Molar cond.* Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	C	H	N	Cl	
[Zn(Salophen)Cl ₂] (Yellow)	59.42 (58.06)	3.55 (3.41)	6.66 (6.77)	14.76 (15.75)	10
[Cd(Salophen)(OAc) ₂] (Yellow)	51.28 (52.91)	3.58 (3.69)	5.32 (5.14)	—	8
[Hg(Salophen)Cl ₂] (Yellow)	45.01 (43.76)	2.69 (2.57)	4.95 (5.10)	12.50 (12.10)	15
[Zn(Nalophen)Cl ₂] (Pale red)	65.99 (65.44)	3.70 (3.53)	5.58 (5.45)	12.65 (12.79)	6
[Cd(Nalophen)(OAc) ₂] (Yellow)	58.42 (59.59)	3.61 (3.74)	4.19 (4.42)	—	12
[Hg(Nalophen)Cl ₂] (Red)	53.01 (51.74)	2.90 (2.80)	4.52 (4.31)	9.75 (10.28)	11
[Zn(Salmphen)Cl ₂] (Brown)	58.52 (58.06)	3.65 (3.41)	6.66 (6.55)	16.10 (15.75)	12

Table—1 (Contd.)

[Hg(Salmphen)Cl ₂] (Brown)	45.01 (43.76)	2.69 (2.57)	4.55 (5.10)	11.95 (12.10)	10
[Zn(Nalmphen)Cl ₂] (Pale red)	65.50 (65.45)	3.50 (3.53)	5.76 (5.45)	12.55 (12.79)	15
[Cd(Nalmphen)(OAc) ₂] (Red)	56.75 (59.59)	3.86 (3.74)	4.45 (4.34)	—	10
[Hg(Nalmphen)Cl ₂] (Yellow)	50.60 (51.74)	2.65 (2.79)	4.65 (4.31)	10.25 (10.28)	9

* $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions in dimethylformamide.

formamide, dichloromethane and dimethylsulphoxide, and slightly in hot ethanol. The low molar conductivities of solution ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) of the complexes prepared using dimethylformamide in the range 5–20 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicate their non-electrolytic nature⁶.

Free Schiff base ligands show weak intramolecular hydrogen bonding (O...H-N) which give rise to a broad absorption band at 3 450 (Salophen), 3 435 (Salmphen), 3 474 (Nalophen) and 3 454 cm^{-1} (Nalmphen) in their respective infrared spectra. These bands disappear in all the Schiff base complexes indicating the bond formation between phenolic oxygen and metal ion. Some important ir bands of the ligands and complexes are presented in Table 2. Strong bands due to C=N stretching for the free ligands slightly shift to higher frequencies ($\Delta\nu = 2\text{--}10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in their metal complexes. It has been found⁷ that C=N⁺ groups have in general higher frequencies than the parent C=N groups. Thus the results are consistent with the presence of charge-separated forms. Hence coordination takes place through negatively charged phenolic oxygen atoms rather than positively charged nitrogen atoms of azomethine groups, since there is no downward shift of azomethine group on complex formation. This in part may arise due to large size of Group IIB metal ions present in the complexes. Sharp ir bands due to C-O stretching for the ligands shift to higher wavenumbers ($\Delta\nu = 9\text{--}50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complex formation. On comparing the ir spectra of the cobalt complexes³ with these tetradentate Schiff base ligands one can observe that the C=N stretching vibration of the ligand has fallen on complex formation and C-O stretching vibration increased to higher frequency. Bonding by phenolic oxygen and chlorine atoms is further corroborated

by the appearance of M-O and M-Cl vibration in the far-ir spectra (Table 2) of the metal complexes.

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$
Salophen	3 450	1 611	1 115	—	—
[Zn(Salophen)Cl ₂]	—	1 615	1 126	340	289
[Cd(Salophen)(OAc) ₂]	—	1 616	1 145	325	—
[Hg(Salophen)Cl ₂]	—	1 621	1 150	338	260
Nalophen	3 474	1 611	1 141	—	—
[Zn(Nalophen)Cl ₂]	—	1 615	1 162	339	300
[Cd(Nalophen)(OAc) ₂]	—	1 617	1 161	340	—
[Hg(Nalophen)Cl ₂]	—	1 620	1 178	338	295
Salmphen	3 435	1 622	1 107	—	—
[Zn(Salmphen)Cl ₂]	—	1 625	1 116	328	300
[Hg(Salmphen)Cl ₂]	—	1 626	1 115	336	298
Nalmphen	3 454	1 618	1 137	—	—
[Zn(Nalmphen)Cl ₂]	—	1 624	1 202	323	300
[Cd(Nalmphen)(OAc) ₂]	—	1 623	1 160	340	—
[Hg(Nalmphen)Cl ₂]	—	1 628	1 214	337	297

Evidence for the presence of acetate ligands in the Cd complex comes from its ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆; Me₄Si) : δ 13.05 (2H, s, =NH⁺), 8.62 (2H, s, =CH), 7.38–6.88 (12H, m, phenyl) and 2.05 (6H, s, acetate) for [Cd(Salophen)(CH₃COO)₂]; for [Cd(Nalophen)(CH₃COO)₂]; δ 13.05 (2H, s, NH⁺), 8.59 (2H, s, =CH), 7.93–6.99 (16H, m, naphthyl and phenyl) and 2.10 (6H, s, acetate).

Therefore, the results are consistent with those of structurally identified zwitterionic complexes² with salicylaldehyde ethylenediimine (Salen). Based

on the above discussion tetracoordinate structure for the Zn and Hg complexes and hexacoordinate structure for the Cd complexes may be suggested.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. Ligands Salophen, Nalophen, Salmphen and Nalmphen were prepared by refluxing the aromatic diamines with the corresponding *o*-hydroxyaldehydes in ethanolic medium for 2 h. The metal salts ZnCl₂, Cd(CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O and HgCl₂ were of A.R. grade.

The complexes were prepared by the addition of the stoichiometric (M : L, 1 : 1) amounts of the metal salt solution to a hot ethanolic solution of Schiff base ligand. The resulting complexes were washed with hot ethanol and hexane and dried over CaCl₂ (yields 36–71%). Analyses and spectral measurements were carried out as described elsewhere⁴. ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer at room temperature.

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